

Hybrid plasmonic bioresins and dECM-based materials for volumetric bioprinting of vascular-inspired architectures

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ABSTRACT. Synergizing nanomaterials technology with advanced 3D printing techniques creates new opportunities for developing smart, stimuli-responsive materials suitable for tissue engineering scaffolds. By incorporating stimuli-responsive nanoparticles into extracellular matrix mimetics, these composites gain functional elements capable of replicating dynamic biological processes *in vitro*. Herein, we propose combining hybrid multifunctional inorganic-organic materials with the emerging Volumetric Bioprinting (VBP) technique. We present two hybrid materials, a light stimuli-responsive polymer-based resin and a biocompatible porcine-derived decellularized extracellular matrix (dECM)-based bioresin, thus expanding the library of materials suitable for VBP. Plasmonic nanoparticles are combined with a thermoresponsive polymeric matrix formulating the stimuli-responsive plasmonic resin, while a dECM-based bioresin with embedded smooth muscle cells (SMCs) is employed for including the biological component to the system. As proof-of-concept to demonstrate the versatility of the hybrid materials, we investigated the generation of highly complex structures, including multi-walled channels, using sequential VBP. Overall, this study broadens the range of materials compatible with VBP, thereby enabling the use of smart multi-component materials in the fabrication of dynamic, stimuli-responsive 3D *in vitro* models.

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INTRODUCTION

Developing novel materials and 3D bioprinting technologies is paramount for the generation of functional biological constructs.^{1,2} In this regard, certain 3D bioprinting attributes are essential including printing speed and avoidance of factors that may negatively affect cellular viability and functionality, printing resolution and scalability, ability to printing multi-materials with minimal sample handling, and the ability to achieve layer-free transitions during curing. The integration of extrusion and droplet-based deposition methods with light-based vat-polymerization techniques such as Digital Light Processing (DLP) and stereolithography (SLA), has led to significant improvements. However, whilst both of these approaches enable the layer-by-layer fabrication of complex, biomimetic cellular structures spanning diverse sizes and resolutions,³⁻⁵ they are generally slow and the sequential exposure of cells to repeated UV/visible light curing can reduce cell viability, in addition to integrating non-homogeneous layered transitions. In addition, both DLP and SLA lack flexibility with regards to multi-material support-free bioprinting. To address these problems, Volumetric Bioprinting (VBP) has emerged as a versatile method to create centimeter-scale cellularized models with high resolution using hydrogel-based photoresins.⁶ Via tomographic back-projections of visible light, volumetric polymerization of photopolymer resins is achieved with uniform resolution and lack of layer-by-layer transitions.^{7,8} To achieve rapid, precise and homogenous photopolymerization, their physical and optical properties including transparency, light-curing efficiency, and photopolymerization kinetics must be controlled.^{7,9} In addition, viscosity values $> 10 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$ are essential to effectively counteract the settling of solidified features (e.g. cells) during the printing process.¹⁰ Due to their excellent rheological properties and success in extrusion bioprinting, numerous gelatin-based materials^{6,11-13}, as well as photo-clickable polyvinyl alcohol (PVA)¹⁴, silk hydrogels¹⁵ and decellularized extracellular matrix (dECM)

bioinks^{16–18} are being explored as VBP resins. Various examples of cellularized bioresins exist, namely for the printing of immortalized cell lines, (e.g., C2C12¹⁵), human mesenchymal stem cells (hMSC)¹⁹, and organoids²⁰, thus replicating features of different tissues *in vitro*.

A promising advancement in the field of bioprinting is the emergence of 4D bioprinting^{21–24} which employs advanced materials, such as shape-memory polymers, to fabricate dynamic tissue analogs that evolve over time or can respond to external stimuli. An alternative methodology employing hybrid bioinks, exploiting the role of nanoparticles (NPs) acting as antennas for the induction of local stimuli-responsive features, offers enhanced functionality and versatility in bioprinting applications.²⁵ Among the various types of NPs compatible with organic matrices, functionalized plasmonic gold NPs (AuNPs), and more specifically gold nanorods (AuNRs), presenting defined localized surface plasmon resonances (LSPR) in the near infrared (NIR) have demonstrated potential for several *in situ* and non-invasive biological applications including biosensing, bioimaging, and photothermal applications.²⁶ Progress in AuNR synthesis and functionalization has allowed the development of highly monodisperse AuNRs with controllable physicochemical properties supporting their homogenous incorporation in organic matrices.²⁷ Their combination with thermosensitive polymers can be taken advantage of to produce mechanical changes in the polymer matrix upon laser irradiation using a light wavelength in resonance with the AuNRs LSPR²⁸. By applying pulsed stimuli, such physical changes can be designed in an on/off manner similar to tissue expansion and contract occurring during physiological processes such as arterial pulsation. Whilst the use of nanoparticulate silica in volumetric printing has been described,^{29,30} to the best of our knowledge the application of hybrid materials featuring inorganic NPs in organic matrices for the printing of stimuli-responsive models via VBP has yet to be described.

In this work, we aimed to expand the range of materials processable through VBP by introducing two novel hybrid resins tailored for the fabrication of *in vitro* vascular models. Specifically, we focused on a gelatin methacryloyl (GelMA)-based formulation, chosen due to its high biocompatibility and tunable viscosity. The first hybrid bioresin comprised GelMA combined with porcine pulmonary artery-derived dECM, resulting in a low-viscosity bioresin blend conducive to the growth and spreading of vascular smooth muscle cells (vSMC). This combination of GelMA and dECM allowed us to preserve desirable mechanical properties for printing whilst incorporating the native tissue composition for the development of tissue-specific models.^{31,32} Following previous approaches, the second bioresin was designed to be stimuli-responsive, incorporating light-responsive and multimodal AuNRs in a thermoresponsive polymer.²⁸ Such hybrid inorganic-organic biomaterials offer a high degree of flexibility in which the physicochemical properties of each component can be tailored. By incorporating GelMA and the necessary photoinitiator in both bioresins, this design allowed us to control the degree of inter-resin crosslinking, thus developing an interjoined multilayered model of biological relevance. This work provides an important advancement in the field of 3D printing of hybrid and stimuli-responsive materials for the development of 4D tissue models.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Volumetric bioprinting of a hybrid organic-inorganic stimuli-responsive ink. We employed a multi-component polymeric blend consisting of N-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAm), poly(ethylene glycol) diacrylate (PEGDA), poly(ethylene glycol) dimethacrylate (PEGDMA), and GelMA.³³ Similar to previously described work, NIPAm conferred stimuli-responsiveness to the resin²⁸, PEGDA and PEGDMA were chosen to adjust the lower critical solution temperature (LCST) closer to physiological body temperature, ensure a rapid

photopolymerization and enhanced hydrogel elasticity, and GelMA introduced cooling-induced gelation and promoted material biocompatibility. Lithium phenyl-2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl-phosphinate (LAP) was included as the photoinitiator. The hybrid nature of the ink was conferred by the inclusion of AuNPs, serving as antennas for the light-stimulated plasmonic-derived nanoheating.³⁴ The incorporation of NPs into resins for VBP poses challenges due to light scattering and absorption during photopolymerization, which can reduce printing resolution, affect gel stiffness, disrupt crosslinking, and extend curing time.^{35,36} By precisely controlling the shape and size of plasmonic NPs, their LSPR can be tuned to avoid interference with the UV/blue (365/405 nm) light sources commonly used to initiate polymerization in light-based printing. Thus, we first verified that the inclusion of AuNPs did not negatively affect VBP performance. We synthesized AuNRs featuring two characteristic plasmon bands, a longitudinal band at 790 nm and a less prominent transversal band at around 520 nm, with minimal absorption at 405 nm (**Figure 1A**). Considering the size of the NPs, $82.8.6 \pm 7.1 \times 24.4 \pm 3.6$ nm (**Figure S1**), we hypothesized that they could also act as scattering elements, similar to cells or subcellular structures, thereby potentially affecting printing resolution.²⁰ We thus printed thermoresponsive gels with a sinusoidal shape, using plasmonic resin (with AuNRs) and polymeric resin (without AuNRs), observing the minimum light dose required to achieve crosslinking and retain shape fidelity. Whilst finely resolved structures were obtained after crosslinking gels without AuNPs with a dose of 200 mJ/cm^2 , the minimal light dose required for crosslinking AuNP-containing gels was 300 mJ/cm^2 (**Figure S2A**). Thus, when integrating NPs into the formulation, we observed the necessity to increase the light dose in order to maintain printing resolution, possibly due to the scattering of part of the incident light by the NPs (**Figure S2B**). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) verified the porous nature of the polymerized hybrid gel, desired for rapid and effective heat diffusion throughout the 3D printed structure, in addition to diffusion of nutrients and gases supporting healthy cell growth (**Figure**

1C). Additionally, we employed multiphoton confocal microscopy to characterize the plasmonic resins, taking advantage of the strong two-photon excited photoluminescence (2PEL) signal generated by the embedded AuNRs under multiphoton laser excitation (**Figure 1B, S3**). We proceeded to print a cylindrical structure (1.2 cm height, 0.6 cm diameter) incorporating a venous valve to prove the feasibility of employing VBP to print more complex and relevant 3D structures with plasmonic resins (**Figure 1D**). As expected, the presence of AuNPs required higher light doses (325 mJ/cm^2 vs 200 mJ/cm^2 for polymeric resins) to photopolymerize the structure with accurate printing resolution (**Figure S4**). Details on the light doses required for printing each specific geometry are summarized in **Table S1**. We proceeded to confirm the thermosensitive nature of the sinusoidal-shaped and venous valve constructs, ensuring that expansion and contraction occurred above and below the LCST ($\sim 36 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) using a hot-plate setup. After 5 minutes of heating at $\sim 39 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, both structures exhibited significant contraction which was reversible upon cooling to below the LCST (**Figure S5A**). Above the LCST, for the sinusoidal-shaped construct, the outer diameter decreased by approximately 0.8 mm, and the venous valve model showed an $\sim 1 \text{ mm}$ reduction in height ($\sim 8.5\%$). It should be emphasized that the observed expansion and contraction resulted from the thermosensitive nature of the polymeric blend, irrelevant of the plasmonic AuNR component. To validate the plasmonic heating capability of the plasmonic resin, we thus proceeded to expose the venous valve to continuous wave (CW) laser irradiation using an 808 nm laser source in close resonance with the LSPR of the AuNRs and ensuring that the laser spot size matched the printed structure's diameter. By controlling the laser power density (ranging from 0.4 to 1.25 W/cm^2), we were able to control the maximum temperature reached in a reversible manner (**Figure S5B**). These initial trials highlight the multimodal nature of AuNRs as contrast agents and as antennas for controlled thermoresponsive behaviors in biologically-relevant 3D models.

Figure 1. Plasmonic resin characterization. A) AuNR characterization by UV – vis spectroscopy with transverse and longitudinal LSPRs shown. B) Porosity of polymerized resin shown via SEM (scale bars: 50 μm and insert 100 μm). C) 2PEL tile image of sinusoidal-shaped model cross-section (scale bar: 1 mm). D) Digital model and the resulting venous valve construct printed using plasmonic resin and VBP (scale bar: 1 mm).

Volumetric bioprinting of living hybrid construct. GelMA has emerged as a versatile photo-crosslinkable biomaterial and gold standard for various light-based biofabrication techniques, including conventional extrusion printing and VBP, owing to its excellent biocompatibility and integrin-binding domains (e.g., RGD).^{6,37–39} However, for applications

requiring cell reorganization of the ECM, dECM-based materials derived from biological tissues through enzymatic, physical, or chemical removal of cellular components (e.g., nucleic acids, proteins, lipids, and membranes) offer superior biological properties by mimicking the native tissue environment.^{18,40,41} In VBP, native tissue analogs have been fabricated using visible light-mediated photo-crosslinking of dECM via ruthenium and sodium persulfate (Ru/SPS), which convert tyrosine residues into di-tyrosine covalent networks.^{16,17} However, this approach is restricted to collagen-rich tissues, and unmodified dECM bioinks often suffer from insufficient mechanical strength and reduced printability at low concentrations. To address these limitations, we explored the VBP potential of a bioresin combining dECM with GelMA, designed to preserve the native tissue composition while enhancing mechanical properties and printability, providing a promising solution for creating robust, biomimetic constructs. The concentration of both components was optimized to ensure transparency and printing resolution, mechanical stability, and material softness to provide an environment optimal for cell growth. For that, four different bioresins were formulated, comprising 5% and 3% (w/v) GelMA hydrogels both with and without 0.1% (w/v) dECM. All formulations were successfully printed using the sinusoidal model (**Figure S6**). We observed that the incorporation of dECM required higher light doses, as did lower GelMA concentrations, presumably due to the lower proportion of methacrylate groups for polymerization (**Table S1**). We focused on the formulation containing dECM and a lower concentration of GelMA (3% w/v), which demonstrated high printing resolution for the sinusoidal-shaped models (**Figure S2**) and enabled successful printing the simplified venous valve model using the same light dose, as observed by brightfield and light sheet imaging (**Figure 2A**).

Following the successful demonstration of printing biologically relevant soft hydrogels with complex geometrical features, the feasibility of producing cell-laden constructs was studied. To

print cylindrical structures measuring 1 cm in height, with and without integrated venous valves, human pulmonary artery-derived smooth muscle cells (SMCs), the predominant cell type of blood vessels, were embedded in the dECM-resin supplemented with LAP (0.1% w/v), at a concentration of $1.5 \cdot 10^6$ cells/mL. When printing the valve structure with cell-loaded bioresins, we observed that a minimum light dose of 280 mJ/cm^2 was necessary for crosslinking the single cell suspensions, primarily to counteract the light scattering effects mediated by the cells.⁴² To produce simple tubular structures without the presence of geometrically complex features such as the valve leaflets, a light dose of 200 mJ/cm^2 was sufficient (**Figure 2B**). **Table S1** provides a summary of the light doses necessary to print each resin formulation and geometry. Significant cell spreading was observed after 1 week, particularly in both the outer and inner surfaces, suggesting that the combination of the established printing parameters and resin composition fostered an optimal environment for cell growth. We observed a significant increase in cellular actin expression over time, with cells exhibiting elongated morphology and forming 3D networks indicative of the development towards functional tissue (**Figure 2C, D; Figure S7**). We observed that the SMC-laden resin exhibited high cell viability and proliferation over time within the printed constructs (**Figure 2E**).

Figure 2. VBP of dECM-based bioresin. A) Venous valve printed using SMC embedded dECM-based bioresin, as shown by stereomicroscopy (left) and light sheet (right) imaging (scale bars: 1 mm). B) Light sheet microscope characterization of perfusable cylindrical construct (scale bar: 1 mm). C) Base of the venous valve showing elongated morphology of embedded SMCs via phalloidin (red) and DAPI (cyan) staining (scale bars: 1 mm (left), 100 μm (top) and 200 μm (bottom)). D) Phalloidin and DAPI staining of SMCs after 1 (left) and 7 (right) days *in vitro* (scale bars: 50 μm). E) Cell viability through live/dead cell fluorescence imaging of the VBP constructs 1 (left) and 7 (right) days post-printing (scale bars: 1 mm).

Multimaterial volumetric bioprinting of hybrid constructs. Having identified two formulations suitable for printing structures with high shape fidelity, we further explored the advantages of VBP to create multilayered bioengineered constructs. With the objective to achieve a bilayered cylinder resembling the architecture of blood vessels (**Figure 3A**), and in which each layer is chemically bound to each other, we first explored printing geometry. Whilst the dECM resin represented the tunica intima layer, the hybrid plasmonic resin was employed to mimic either the tunica adventitia (Model 1) or the internal elastic lamellae (Model 2) (**Figure**

3B). To promote the chemical union between both layers and based on the hypothesis that some GelMA methacrylate groups may remain unreacted after the first photopolymerization step, we configured the secondary photopolymerization step to overlap on the 1st printed material by 100 μm (**Figure S8A**). This technique would theoretically ensure crosslinking between layers, promoting stable, multi-layered concentric tubular construct formation upon printing the second material.

Using the previously reported sequential strategy for multi-material VBP⁴³, we proceeded to print 1 cm high layered tubular constructs, first printing the inner layer followed by the outer layer regardless of the model chosen (Model 1 or 2) (**Figure S8B**). To ensure correct alignment of the second material printed, a slightly over-photopolymerized (350-400 mJ/cm^2) circular base was included in the design of the first printed material. This base stabilized the structure in the printing vial, allowing non-photopolymerized resin to be rinsed away using PBS buffer and ensuring precise positioning for the second material. The base was easily removed with a razor blade upon completion of printing. As observed by the stereomicroscope, light sheet, and confocal multiphoton-fluorescence imaging, the optimized printing strategy and light doses enabled the fabrication of the two proposed blood vessel models (**Figure 3C, D**). Again, by exploiting the 2PEL of AuNRs, we were able to distinctly image both the AuNR-containing hybrid layers and the dECM-based layers stained with Cy3.5 (**Figure S9**). This approach facilitated simultaneous evaluation of the printing resolution of each layer and the overall structure, enabling structural characterization of the printed constructs without the need for additional dyes. Notably, the incorporation of the venous valve within the inner layer of each model was also achieved (**Figure 3C-D(iv)**). Details of all light doses used can be found in **Table S2**.

Figure 3. Multi-layered VBP of hybrid materials. A) Schematic representation of the layered structure of native arteries. B) Illustration and macroscopic images of resins in VBP printing vials. (C) Model 1 (tunica adventitia, plasmonic resin; tunica media, dECM resin), and (D) Model 2 (tunica media, dECM bioresin; internal elastic layer, plasmonic resin), imaged using (i) stereomicroscopy images (scale bars: 1 mm), (ii) light sheet (scale bars: 2 mm), and (iii) multiphoton confocal imaging (plasmonic resin shown in white using 2PEL, and dECM resin shown in cyan using incorporated Cy3.5) (scale bars: 1 mm). (iv) The incorporation of a simplified venous valve structure into both models was shown by light sheet microscopy (scale bars: 2 mm).

Multimaterial volumetric bioprinting of hybrid cell-laden constructs. Finally, we studied the integration of SMCs into the dECM bioresin, focusing on Model 1 in which the plasmonic resin mimics the tunica adventitia surrounding the dECM layer. Initially we followed the previously optimized printing strategy in which first the SMC-containing dECM bioresin was

polymerized, followed by removal of unpolymerized resin and addition of the plasmonic resin. However, we were unable to maintain the alignment between the layers and SEM imaging showed lack of cross-linking between both layers (**Figure S10**). Therefore, and to provide an adhesive support to which the softer dECM bioresin could crosslink to, we decided to first print the outer plasmonic resin followed by the inner SMC-containing dECM bioresin. This allowed us to i) maintain printing resolution, ii) achieve crosslinking between layers, and iii) avoid excessive exposure of SMCs to multiple light exposure and unpolymerized plasmonic resin, both of which have a negative effect on cell viability (**Figure S11**). In addition, this strategy allowed us to conduct all printing steps at room temperature, and only after dECM bioink photopolymerization transfer the sample to 37 °C for thermal gelling of the dECM component and to support cell growth. As expected, after photopolymerization of the plasmonic resin and washing to remove unpolymerized resin, the cylinder remained upright without any displacement. Subsequent addition of the SMC-containing dECM resin and its photopolymerization was successfully achieved, albeit with slightly higher light doses required due to light attenuation from the plasmonic resin (**Figure 4, Figure S12**). All the details of the light doses required for multi-material printing, both with and without embedded cells, are summarized in **Table S2**. The two layers of the model, an outer plasmonic resin and an inner dECM-layer with embedded phalloidin-stained SMCs, are clearly depicted using confocal multiphoton and fluorescence imaging (**Figure 4A**). Using SEM imaging, and as previously verified using lightsheet and multiphoton-fluorescent imaging (**Figure 3**), we observed that the layers are positioned adjacent to each other and remain attached to one another, suggestive of interlayer binding (**Figure 4B**). Notably, cells were homogeneously distributed throughout the cylindrical construct, exhibiting high post-printing viability, quantified at approximately 75% using the Live/Dead assay, and demonstrated continued proliferation over the experimental period (**Figure 4C, D**).

Figure 4. Microscopic characterization of cell embedded multi-layered constructs. A) Orthogonal maximum intensity projection of a z-stack showing the outer plasmonic resin layer (2PEL, white) and the inner SMC embedded dECM bioresin layer (phalloidin-actin and DAPI-nuclei in red and cyan, respectively) (scale bars: 1 mm (top), and 200 μm (bottom)). B) Concentric cylinder cross-section imaged by SEM showing the dECM bioresin and the outer porous plasmonic resin (scale bar: 100 μm). C) Cell viability assessed through live/dead cell fluorescence imaging 24 h post-printing (scale bar: 100 μm). D) Phalloidin (red) and DAPI (cyan) staining of SMCs after 1 (left) and 7 (right) days *in vitro* (scale bars: 200 μm).

CONCLUSION

This study expands the library of materials suitable for VBP. To prove the versatility of hybrid inorganic-organic materials in additive manufacturing and broaden their range of applications, we explored the generation of biologically relevant structures through VBP. Through the optimization of resin composition, VBP light dose, and printing order, we successfully demonstrated for the first time the ability to print complex geometries using plasmonic resins. Employing the SMC-loaded dECM-based hybrid bioresin, we successfully printed with high cell viability and appropriate cell morphology biologically relevant structures, namely a multilayered cylinder and venous valve replicating components of the human vasculature. Nonetheless, considerable potential for improvement remains. To facilitate printing and promote the inter-layer binding of the plasmonic and dECM resins, we incorporated GelMA in both. While this approach was still conducive to cell proliferation and maintenance of the SMC phenotype, future studies should explore methods to increase the proportion of dECM to further enhance SMC biological activity. Additionally, we foresee that the structure presented in Model 2, plasmonic resin as the internal elastic lamellae inspired layer surrounded by the SMC-containing tunica media layer, could have promising applications as a platform supporting endothelialization within the model. Given the inherent challenges in achieving endothelialization of blood vessel analogs and the mechano-sensitivity of endothelial cells towards arterial wall stiffening, the incorporation of plasmonic resin mimicking the internal elastic lamellae could represent a novel and promising solution. The tunable stiffness and stimuli-responsiveness of the plasmonic resin may foster an environment favorable for promoting endothelial cell adhesion and facilitating the development of a functional monolayer featuring tight junctions. This approach is particularly relevant where actin remodeling of endothelial cells becomes more organized on stiffer substrates, resulting in the regulation of

assembly and disassembly of VE-cadherin-based junctions.⁴⁴ In future directions, various cell types including fibroblasts in the outermost layer and endothelial cell in the lumen should be integrated into the multilayered model to create a more heterotypic artery microenvironment, fostering cell-cell and cell extracellular matrix interactions. VBP of methacrylated dECMs represents another strategy for enhancing the mechanical properties of 3D bioprinted dECM constructs, thereby removing the need of combining it with additional materials (e.g. GelMA). So far, liver⁴⁵, skeletal muscle¹⁶ and cartilage⁴⁶ derived dECMs have been reported to be methacrylated, indicating their potential use as bioinks efficacy as bioinks for diverse bioprinting applications. However, VBP constructs that combine dECMs of various origins with GelMA can extend applications to tissues with low collagen content such as brain or kidney, while enhancing mechanical properties and cell responsiveness and preserving dECM bioactivity. These constructs offer physiologically relevant platforms for studying disease mechanisms, advancing personalized medicine, and enabling drug screening. We have shown how VBP can be employed to print complex structures that can be remotely stimulated to mimic natural functions, such as arterial pulsation, using NIR laser irradiation. Exploring the mechanical operation of 3D-printed valves to enable dynamic responses could further enhance their utility. The combination of highly tuneable, stimuli-responsive hybrid materials with VBP technology holds significant potential for replicating physiological and pathological conditions with precision and versatility.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Materials. Hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB, $\geq 99.0\%$), hydrogen tetrachloroaurate trihydrate ($\text{HAuCl}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\geq 99.9\%$), silver nitrate (AgNO_3 , $\geq 99.9\%$), L-ascorbic acid (AA, $\geq 99\%$), sodium borohydride (NaBH_4 , 99%), N-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAm, 97%), poly(ethylene glycol) diacrylate (PEGDA, average $M_n=700$), Poly(ethylene

glycol) dimethacrylate (average $M_n=550$), 0.5% trypsin/EDTA solution (10X), penicillin-streptomycin (P/S, 10,000 U/mL), 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI, 1 mg/mL), actin-555 ReadyProbes, ethidium homodimer-1 (EthD-1), calcein acetoxymethyl (calcein AM), paraformaldehyde (PFA), were all purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific. Lithium phenyl-2,4,6-trimethylbenzoylphosphinate (LAP), was obtained from Tokyo Chemical Industry, Japan Human Pulmonary Artery Smooth Muscle Cells (SMCs, ATCC-PCS-100-023), Vascular Cell Basal Media (ATCC-PCS-100-030), and Vascular Smooth Muscle Cell growth supplements (ATCC-PCS-100-023) were purchased from ATCC. All chemicals were used as received and Milli-Q water was used in all experiments. All glassware used for AuNRs synthesis was washed with aqua regia, rinsed with water and dried before use.

Plasmonic resin preparation and characterization

Nanoparticle Synthesis and characterization. Following a previously established protocol, NP synthesis was conducted using a microfluidic flow reactor setup.⁴⁷ Seeds were prepared by the rapid reduction of a 20 mL HAuCl_4 1 mM solution in 100 mM CTAB, using a 2.4 mL NaBH_4 12 mM aqueous solution. Two HPLC pumps and a total flow rate of 11.2 mL/min was maintained within the reactor for the preparation of the seeds, which were kept at RT for 30 minutes to remove the borohydride excess. All three pumps of the reactor were employed for the synthesis of AuNRs. For the growth of the AuNRs, a 50 mL solution of 100 mM CTAB containing 1 mM HAuCl_4 and 0.24 mM AgNO_3 under acidic conditions (pH 3 ~ 4) were mixed with a 25 mL solution of 3.2 mM ascorbic acid in 100 mM CTAB. Following Au (III) pre-reduction to Au (I) in the mixing tube, 25 mL of 100 mM CTAB containing 800 μL of seeds were added, with a 20 mL/min total system flow rate. The resulting solution was left undisturbed for 4 h before centrifuging the colloidal dispersion at 8000 rpm for 20 minutes and redispersing the AuNRs in a 1 mM CTAB solution. This method resulted in AuNRs with a

maximum absorbance at 790 nm, observed in the UV–vis–NIR extinction spectra (Agilent 8453 UV–vis diode-array spectrophotometer). AuNR characterization via Transmission Electron Microscope (JEOL JEM-1400PLUS) operating at 120 kV, was conducted by drop casting on a carbon-coated 400 square mesh Cu grid. Hydrated polymerized plasmonic resins were imaged using Environmental Scanning Electron Microscopy (eSEM-FEI QUANTA 250) working at an acceleration voltage of 30 kV, under a pressure of 70 Pa.

Polymeric ink development. The thermoresponsive plasmonic resin was prepared by mixing, in a 3:1 ratio, two concentrated solutions including a stock of NIPAm, PEGDA and PEGDMA and the other one of GelMA with AuNRs. Briefly, for reaching the desired final concentration, 21.33% (w/v) NIPAm and 8% (w/v) PEGDA were added into PBS (10 mM, pH 7.4), and dissolved upon magnetic stirring and sonication at RT. PEGDMA (2.66%, v/v) was then introduced to the first solution, and complete homogenization was achieved upon centrifugation at 5000 rpm for 5 minutes. The resulting formulations can be stored at this point at 4 °C until needed. For the GelMA - AuNRs solution, 20% (w/v) GelMA was dissolved in PBS under vigorous stirring at 45 °C. Separately, the AuNR solution was gently washed twice, by centrifugation at 8000 rpm for 10 minutes, and resuspended in milliQ water, to eliminate the excess of CTAB. The AuNR concentration was adjusted during washing to achieve the desired concentration of 2 mM when combined with the GelMA. The washed AuNR solution was added drop by drop to the dissolved GelMA gel under stirring, ensuring that the color of the final gel matched the color of the AuNRs in solution. For the final gel preparation, the GelMA - AuNR solution was added drop by drop to the concentrated thermoresponsive mixture under continuous stirring in a 3:1 ratio. The resulting plasmonic formulation, containing 16% (w/v) NIPAm, 8% (w/v) PEGDA, 0-2% (v/v) PEGDMA, 5% (w/v) GelMA and 0,5 mM AuNRs, was stored at 4 °C until needed, and just before its use, the photoinitiator, 0.1% (w/v) LAP, was

freshly added to the gel. The final AuNR concentration (0.5 mM) was chosen based on previous work in which gel transparency and heating efficiency were optimized.²⁸

dECM-based bioresin preparation and characterization

Cell culture. Human Pulmonary Artery Smooth Muscle Cells (SMCs) were cultured in vascular cell basal media supplemented with vascular smooth muscle growth supplements and used between passages 3 and 12. The cells were trypsinized using 0.5x trypsin-EDTA.

dECM – GelMA bioresin formulation. Different compositions were prepared by varying the concentration of the dECM and GelMA for assessing the printing resolution of the bioresins. Both the dECM and GelMA (80% degree of functionalization) were synthesized and combined as previously reported³³, and supplemented with fresh 0.1% (w/v) LAP to initiate the photo-crosslinking reaction upon VBP. In short, 10% (w/v) GelMA and 1% (w/v) dECM stocks were diluted in PBS to final concentrations of 5% and 3% (w/v) for the GelMA and by working on ice, to 0.1% (w/v) in the case of the dECM. To ensure sterility and avoid contamination, the bioink was filtered with a 0.2 µm pore filter. SMCs were mixed with the dECM-based formulation to a final concentration of 1.5×10^6 cells/mL to form the SMC bioresin.

Volumetric Bioprinting (VBP) of models.

A commercial volumetric printer (Tomolite v1.0, Readily3D SA, Switzerland) was employed to fabricate the constructs. The resins were added to 10 mm OD flat bottom BK7 glass vials (Readily3D SA, Switzerland) and thermally gelled in ice-cold water prior to printing. The custom-designed CAD files (Fusion360) were loaded and processed using the Readily3D Apparite software and the light doses were optimized for each material and model as described. SI Videos 1 and 2 show the printing of the dECM-based resin and hybrid resin layer, respectively. Venous valve models were additionally printed using Apparite's proprietary

settings for a bulk length of 400 μm and a bulk multiplier of 2x. Resins were kept on ice prior to printing. In the case that thermal gelation was required, pre-warmed PBS was used to wash uncrosslinked resins from the polymerized constructs. Otherwise, ice-cold PBS was used for washing.

Cell growth and characterization in 3D model.

The multi-layered printed constructs were incubated at 37 °C and 5 % CO₂ in a humidified incubator, replacing cell media every 2-3 days. A stereoscope was used to observe changes in cell morphology over time.

Multiphoton and fluorescence confocal microscopy. Cell survival within the bioprinted, single dECM-based cylinder and the multilayered concentric layer model, was evaluated with live (green)/dead (red) imaging (calcein, ethidium homodimer, Thermo Fischer) after 1 and 7 days *in vitro* using a Thunder imaging system (Leica Microsystems, Germany). To achieve higher resolution and better differentiate the cell morphology in the constructs, nuclear and actin staining was performed. Samples were fixed (using 4% (w/v) PFA) after 1 and 7 days of culture and stained using DAPI (1/500) and Actin 555 ReadyProbe (1/60) at 4 °C overnight. A Zeiss LSM 880 microscope equipped with argon, DPSS, HeNE and MaiTai lasers was employed to determine the structure of the samples fabricated via VBP by fluorescence and multiphoton confocal imaging. Multiphoton imaging was used to image the plasmonic resin taking advantage of the 2PEL of AuNRs. Embedded cells were imaged using phalloidin and DAPI stains and standard excitation/emission wavelengths. Considering the inability to image the valve leaflets via confocal microscopy due to the constructs' height and the working distance limitations of the objectives, and the prior confirmation of the high printing resolution, the cell morphology and distribution within the valves was characterized in the bottom layers of the model. The images were processed with ZEN and ImageJ software.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). A Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope – FESEM (JEOL JSM-IT800) operating at an accelerated voltage of 2 kV and at a working distance of ~4 mm was employed to determine the microstructure and assess the binding of the layers in the 3D printed constructs. The SEM images were colored using Inkscape 1.2 software.

Light sheet Microscopy. dECM-resin was stained with Cy3.5-PEG-SH (Biopharma PEG, USA). Optical sections were taken (Basler a2A1920-160umPRO, Germany) using a custom-built light sheet imaging setup using a 532 nm laser excitation source (Roithner RLDD532-50-3, Austria) and a 600 nm long pass filter. Images were taken with a slice separation of 34 μm and processed with ImageJ software.

Heating experimental setup. A custom heating setup was used for the plasmonic heating of the constructs fabricated through VBP. An 808 nm laser (Lumics, LU808T040) with a spot size of 0.785 cm^2 was utilized to uniformly illuminate the entire valve-containing hybrid construct to analyze its heating properties. An infrared camera (FLIR AX35), capturing images at a rate of 30 Hz, was used to monitor the temperature in real time. The structure, consisting of 1 cm high cylinders with an internal venous valve, was placed in a well of a 48-well plate and immersed in 750 μL of PBS. This arrangement prevents the sample from drying out and simulates cell culture conditions, supporting future experiments with cell-laden constructs. A Heidolph heating plate was used to set the initial temperature, which was maintained at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

The following file is available free of charge (PDF).

Figure S1, TEM images of AuNRs; Figure S2, VBP of sinusoidal-shaped disks under different conditions of the plasmonic resin and dECM-based bioresin to evaluate the printing resolution; Figure S3, 2PEL multiphoton microscopy characterization of sinusoidal-shaped structures with and without AuNRs; Figure S4, Images of the VBP printed venous valve model; Figure S5, Characterization of the thermal response of the plasmonic resin after printing; Figure S6, Sinusoidal-shaped disks of dECM bioresin with different GelMA percentages; Figure S7, Characterization of the SMCs embedded in the dECM-based bioresin at days 1, 3 and 7 after VBP; Figure S8, Digital model of the multi-layered cylindrical structure containing a 100 μm overlap between layers and macroscopic images of the sequential printing; Figure S9, Structural characterization of the different layers of the multilayered VBP models through 2PEL; Figure S10 VBP of cellularized multi-layered cylinders formed from first printing of the inner SMC-containing dECM resin followed by the outer plasmonic resin, which led to misalignment and detachment between the layers shown by optical microscope, SEM, 2PEL and fluorescence confocal images; Figure S11, SMC viability assessed through the live/dead cell fluorescence assay; Figure S12, VBP of final multi-layered cylinder; Table S1, Optimized light-doses of the different resins; Table S2, Details of the light doses required for multi-material printing with and without embedded cells; SV1: Video showing the photo-polymerization of the dECM-based bioresin, SV2: Video showing the photo-polymerization of the hybrid resin layer.

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UAL performed most of the experimental work. All authors analyzed and discussed the results. The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors edited and revised the manuscript. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript. Funding was secured by DJdA.

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Supporting Information

Hybrid plasmonic bioresins and dECM-based materials for volumetric bioprinting of vascular-inspired architectures

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1. Plasmonic nanoparticle characterization

Figure S1. AuNRs (length, 82.8 ± 7.1 nm; width, 24.4 ± 3.6 nm) synthesized in the multifluidic flow reactor characterized via transmission electron microscopy (TEM) (scale bars: 100 nm).

2. Optimization of the printing parameters

2.1 Sinusoidal-shaped disks of plasmonic resin and dECM bioresin.

Figure S2. VBP of sinusoidal-shaped disks. (A) macroscopic image illustrating examples of overcured (*), undercured (), and optimally cured (***) constructs made from plasmonic resin (scale bar: 0.5 cm). (B) Quantitative comparison of printing resolution between the plasmonic resin and the dECM-based bioresin. Lines in stereomicroscopy images highlight the measured strut (n = 3, scale bars: 200 μ m).**

2.2 Microscopy characterization of sinusoidal-shaped disks with and without NPs.

Figure S3. 2PEL multiphoton microscopy characterization of sinusoidal-shaped structures printed using thermoresponsive resin with (left) and without (right) AuNRs (scale bars: left; 1 mm, right; 200 μ m).

2.3 Images of the VBP printed venous valve model

Figure S4. Macroscopic and stereomicroscopy images of the VBP venous valve model constructed using thermoresponsive resins without (top) and with (bottom) AuNRs (Scale bars: 1 mm).

2.4 Thermal response of the plasmonic resin after printing

Figure S5. Thermal response of hybrid constructs upon VBP including (A) a comparison between the expanded ($T = 33\text{ °C}$) and contracted ($T = 39\text{ °C}$) states including a top view of the swirl shape (left) and side view of the venous valve (right) structures, demonstrating their response to temperatures below and above

the LCST of the thermoresponsive components, respectively (scale bars: 1 mm), and (B) temperature profiles at changing laser power densities with red line indicating the LCST of the material ($\sim 36^\circ\text{C}$).

2.5 Sinusoidal-shaped disks of dECM bioresin with GelMA.

Figure S6. Printing resolution of the dECM bioresins with varying GelMA and dECM concentrations as shown through stereomicroscope images in gray scale. (Scale bars: 1 mm).

2.6 Optimized light-doses of different resins

Table S1. Optimized light-doses for VBP of various materials at the desired geometries.

	Material		Shape	Light Dose (mJ/cm ²)
Plasmonic resin	0 mM AuNRs (0.1% LAP)		Swirl	200
	0.5 mM AuNRs (0.1% LAP)		Swirl	300
	0.5 mM AuNRs (0.2% LAP)		Swirl	225
	0.5 mM AuNRs (0.5% LAP)		Swirl	Overexposed
	0 mM AuNRs (0.1% LAP)		Valve	200
	0.5 mM AuNRs (0.1% LAP)		Valve	325
dECM-based bioresin	GelMA 5%		Swirl	130
	GelMA 3%		Swirl	140
	GelMA 5% - dECM 0.1%		Swirl	175
	GelMA 3% - dECM 0.1%		Swirl	250
	GelMA 3% - dECM 0.1%		Valve	250
	GelMA 3% - dECM 0.1% + SMCs		Valve	280
	GelMA 3% - dECM 0.1% + SMCs		Tube	200

3. Cell characterization

Figure S7. Phalloidin and DAPI staining of SMCs embedded in the dECM-based bioresin at days (A) 1, (B) 3 and (C) 7 after VBP (Scale bars: 100 μ m).

4. Multi-material printing

4.1 Printing multi-material models

Figure S8. A) Digital model of the multi-layered cylindrical structure containing a 100 μm overlap between layers and (B) macroscopic images of the sequential VBP of the 2 models comprising multi-layered concentric cylinders.

4.2 Microscopy characterization of the models

Figure S9. Structural characterization of the different layers of the multilayered VBP models through 2PEL (white) and Cy3.5 (cyan) confocal imaging (scale bars: 1 mm).

4.3 Lack of cross-linking between both layers

Figure S10. VBP of cellularized multi-layered cylinders formed from first printing of the inner SMC-containing dECM resin followed by the outer

plasmonic resin, which led to misalignment and detachment between the layers as shown by (A) optical microscope (scale bar: 50 μm), (B) SEM micrograph imaging (scale bars: 200 μm (left) and 100 μm (right)), and (C) 2PEL and fluorescence confocal images for the visualization of the plasmonic resin (white) and SMCs (stained with phalloidin, red, and DAPI, cyan) embedded in the ECM resin (scale bars: 1 mm).

4.4 Toxicity

Figure S11. SMC viability assessed through the live (green)/dead (red) cell fluorescence assay at days (A) 1 and (B) 7 after first printing the inner SMC-containing dECM bioresin followed by the outer plasmonic resin (scale bars: 100 μm).

4.5 Final multi-layered cylinder design

Figure S12. VBP of final multi-layered cylinder upon the sequential printing of the (A) plasmonic resin cylinder containing a slightly overexposed base and subsequent printing of the SMC-embedded dECM bioresin as the inner layer, resulting in (B) concentric cylinders successfully bound to each other (scale bars: 1 mm, 100 μm (top) and 40 μm (bottom)).

4.6 Optimized light-doses for multi-material printing

Table S2. Details of the light doses required for multi-material printing with and without embedded cells.

	Layer (in printing order)	Material	Shape	Light Dose (mJ/cm^2)
Model 1	Inner	GelMA 3% - dECM 0.1%	Tube, base	250, 300
		GelMA 3% - dECM 0.1%	Tube with valve, base	280, 300
	Outer	0.5 mM AuNRs (0.1% LAP)	Tube	300

Model 1 Cells	Outer	0.5 mM AuNRs (0.1% LAP)	Tube, base	260, 300
	Inner	GelMA 3% - dECM 0.1% + SMC	Tube	360
Model 2	Inner	0.5 mM AuNRs (0.1% LAP)	Tube, base	300, 400
		0.5 mM AuNRs (0.1% LAP)	Tube with valve, base	325, 400
	Outer	GelMA 3% - dECM 0.1%	Tube	300

4.7 Videos of the printing process

SV1: Video showing the photo-polymerization of the dECM-based bioresin.

SV2: Video showing the photo-polymerization of the hybrid resin layer.